

Social

A STUDY ON AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOUR AND EMOTIONAL MATURITY OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

Mary Jeba N ^{*1}

^{*1} M.Ed. Scholar, Immanuel Arasar College of Education, India

Abstract

The study intended to find out any relationship between aggressive behavior and emotional maturity of adolescents. Aggressive behavior is the reactionary and impulsive behaviour. The role of education is the modification of behaviour of the individual. So, school has a great role in mending the behaviour of the students. Moral education and mediation can be given to students. This may help them to get rid of the aggressive behaviour. The investigator used the mean, standard deviation, t-test and ANOVA (analysis of variance) to analyze the data and results were tabulated. The adolescent students show more aggressive behaviour than emotional maturity.

Keywords: Educational Psychology; Aggressive Behaviour; Emotions.

Cite This Article: Mary Jeba N. (2018). “A STUDY ON AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOUR AND EMOTIONAL MATURITY OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS.” *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 6(7), 10-15. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1321294>.

1. Introduction

The main aim of education should be to teach us rather how to think, rather to improve our minds, so as to teach us rather how to think, rather to improve our minds, so as to enable us to think for ourselves, than to load the memory with thoughts of other men. Education is what remains after one has forgotten what one has learned in school. Education would be much more effective if its purpose was to ensure that by the time they leave school every boy and girl should know how much they do not know, and be imbued with a lifelong desire to know it.

We focus on the individual student so that he/she has a firm foundation for the rapidly changing and unpredictable world of the future. We achieve a rare combination of high academic performance and a good, friendly relationship between students and their teachers.

2. Educational Psychology

Educational psychology studies the problems of education in terms of psychology. In other words, it is a psychology approach to education. But, it does not mean that educational psychology,

through a phase of education, is quite different from it in certain aspects. Education has a wider field, while functions of educational psychology are limited.

2.1. Aggressive Behaviour

Aggression is a broader concept, involving efforts to harm or control another person; it is manifested quite early in childhood; it then typically undergoes changes in its forms and functions. Aggression is a bio- psycho social phenomenon having biological, cognitive, psychodynamic and social causes. Gilula and Daniels (1969) defines aggression as the entire spectrum of assertive, intrusive, and attacking behaviour and included both overt and covert attempts to master a task or accomplish an act.

During adolescence the aggression takes on different manifestations and functions. Adolescents' self- absorption and prickly sensitivity to the views of others means that acceptance by a peer group takes on increased acceptance, does their own position within the status hierarchy of that group. In addition adolescence take place. These settings may involve greater diversity and competition than the adolescent previously encountered.

2.2. Meaning of Emotions

Emotional maturity is that characteristic of emotional behaviour that is generally attained by an adult after the expiry of his adolescence period. After attaining emotional maturity he is able to demonstrate a well-balanced emotional behaviour in his day -to-day life. A person may be said to be emotionally matured if he has in his able to express them at the appropriate time in an appropriate degree (Dandapani, 2010)

Emotions are the raw material of a character. They are the dynamic of all our actions. The word "emotion" literally means 'movement out' and in many of the observable signs of emotional movement can be seen. Even when the movement cannot be clearly detected by eye, it can sometimes be detected if the physiological changes are investigated.

3. Statement of the Problem

It is essential to develop emotional maturity among the children to develop a sense of direction, awareness of objectives for life. This study tries to find out "Aggressive Behaviour and Emotional Maturity of Adolescent students".

4. Objectives of the Study

- To find out the level of Aggressive behaviour of adolescent with regard to background variables.
- To find out the level of Emotional maturity of adolescent with regard to background variables.
- To find out significant difference if any in the aggressive behaviour of adolescent with regard to background variables.

- To find out significant difference, if any in the Emotional maturity of adolescent students with regard to background variables.
- To find out significant relationship between Aggressive behaviour and Emotional maturity of adolescent students.

4.1. Hypotheses of the Study

- **Ho₈** There is no significant difference in the aggressive behaviour of adolescent students with regard to occupation of father.
- **Ho₉** There is no significant difference in the aggressive behaviour of adolescent students with regard to occupation of mother.
- **Ho₁₀** There is no significant difference in the aggressive behaviour of adolescent students with regard to monthly income of the family
- **Ho₁₁** There is no significant difference in the emotional maturity of adolescent students with regard to gender.

4.2. Significance of the Study

Emotions and behaviour of adolescence needs an attention. Aggressive behaviour is very common in adolescent period. It is essential to develop emotional maturity among the children to develop sense of direction, awareness of objectives for life, to develop organized and integrated emotional response and ability to bear stress under calmness to develop control over emotional maturity and do right thing at the right time. Emotionally mature persons have belief in long – term planning and are capable of delaying or revising their expectations in terms of demands of situations an emotionally mature person has the capacity to make effective adjustment with himself members of his family in school, workplace, society and culture. Emotional maturity leads to general unhappiness as seen in the feeling of fear to failure disappointment frustration stress.

5. Methodology

The present study attempts to explore the level of emotional maturity and aggressive behaviour of adolescents as far as the problem and objectives of the study is concerned the investigation selected survey method for conducting the study.

Schematic Representation of the Research Design

S.I	Types	Source
1	Nature of the study	Survey Method
2	Variables	Emotional Maturity and Aggressive Behavior
3	Tool Used	Standardized tool-Emotional Maturity scale and Aggressive Behavior scale
4	Sample selected for the study	300 (11 th and 12 th standard students)
5	Statistical techniques	Mean, Standard deviation, t-test and F-test

5.1. Data Sampling Design

The sample for the present study comprises of 300 secondary school students studying in various schools of Kanyakumari district. The investigator used random sampling technique to collect data.

5.2. Statistical Techniques Used

Statistical techniques are extensively used in educational research. They provide an indispensable tool for collecting, organizing, analysing and interpreting data expressed in numerical terms. The data collected for the study were analysed by using the following techniques mean, Standard Deviation, t-test, F-test, Correlation analysis, Percentage analysis.

6. Research Findings

Interpretations

- 1) There is no significant difference found in the aggressive behaviour of male and female adolescent students. The mean value shows that male adolescent students are more aggressive than females. This may be due to boys prefer to watch violent movies, imitate their favourite heroes, to get attention from others and also due to hormonal changes.
- 2) Emotional maturity of male early adolescent students are better than females. The possible reason behind this may be male students have more interaction with society, peer groups, neighbours, relations and they learn to accept and adjust with them. This makes the male students to become emotionally mature than female students.
- 3) Early adolescent students from urban locality are studying in urban school shows high aggressive behaviour when compared with rural locality students. This may be due to urban locality students are more exposed to media, watching too much action packed violent programmes on television, watching wrestling shows on TV and internet usage. These can strongly influence the behaviour of early adolescent students.
- 4) Early adolescent's students from rural locality and studying in rural schools show high emotional maturity than urban locality students. This may be due to rural locality students. This may be due to rural locality students are more attached with peer group, family members and society. They may get more chance to share their feelings with others. This will help them to develop emotionally mature character.
- 5) The mean value shows aggressive behaviour of early adolescent's students in private schools is higher than others. The reason may be due to school atmosphere has a great importance in child's behaviour. Govt and private schools are different due to their economic status, infrastructural facilities, teachers, curriculum etc. these elements create a variation in between Govt and private schools which affect the aggression level of adolescent students.
- 6) There is significant difference noticed in educational qualification of parents and aggressive behaviour of adolescent students. This may be due to non-educated parents are more passive. They do not deal with issues of children properly. This will create aggressive behaviour in adolescent students.
- 7) There is no significant difference found in educational qualification of parents and emotional maturity in adolescent students. This may be due to qualified parents provide all

the provision of their children. Parents will give proper training and discipline at home. This will help the students to become emotionally mature in nature.

- 8) Early adolescent children's parents working as coolie and housewife show more aggressive behaviour. The reason may be due to children is getting too little support of parent's foe doing homework, activities and financial support. This will create aggressive behaviour in education.
- 9) Emotional maturity of early adolescent students of parents working as coolie and private sector is high. This may be due to parents are giving good advices to the children, children are more over about the sufferings of parents. So they are emotionally mature in nature.
- 10) Early adolescent children having monthly income below 5000 shows high aggressive behaviour. This reason may be due to parents are unable to provide children's needs. When the students see other children's facilities they will create depression are aggressive behaviour in class.

7. Recommendations and Implications

Aggressive behaviour is the reactionary and impulsive behaviour. The role of education is the modification of behaviour of the individual. So school has a great role in mending the behaviour of the students. Moral education and mediation can be given to students. This may help them to get rid of the aggressive behaviour.

The teachers are more responsible in reducing the aggressive behaviour of students. The teacher should act as a friend and guide. There should be a good rapport between the teacher and students. So that students may approach the teacher in discussing their personal problem and behaviour. So that proper counselling can be given to students. Teacher can instruct and suggest the students to watch useful programmers on television and play computer and video games which do not kindle the aggressive behaviour of the students.

Parents should keep an eye on their children not to watch violent programmes on television, interest and not to play violent computer and video games. Schools can organize community service programmes which map help the students to know the weaker section of the society and to helps them to modify them parents can also teach god values to help others and they should exhibit good behaviour before their children.

Teacher must play an important role in developing emotional maturity of the students. They should make the children gradually learn how to cope with real life. The students should be train to realize and respect the emotions of others. Classes on value education and personality. Development can be conducted in schools to inculcate new values and create leadership questions. Teachers can create a positive classroom environment. This may create self-confidence among the children.

The student teachers can be trained to develop the emotional maturity of them and so that in may be helpful for the students they teach in the future. Seminars and workshops can be conducted in colleges of education to enhance the emotional maturity of the student teacher.

Teachers and parents can suggest the students to watch media programmers that are informative and that do not destroy the emotional maturity of the students. Parents are the first teachers they

should inculcated proper values to their children through their behaviours. They can act as good friends for their children so that they express themselves to parents. Everyday parents should spend time with their children and discuss with them the happening of the day. The suggestions from the parents can help the children them to maintain the emotional stability.

8. Conclusion

The aggressive behaviour is more significant in adolescent student due to the qualification and occupation of the parents and with regard to the in monthly income. They do not deals the issues of the children properly and children do not get proper support from the parents for doing homework, activities and financial problem. So the adolescent students show more aggressive behaviour than emotional maturity.

References

- [1] Aggarwal, J.C. (2005). Essential of educational psychology, UBS, New Delhi Kothari, C.R. (2011).
- [2] Agarwal, Y.P (1988), Statistical Method-concepts, Applications and computations. New Delhi: Sterling Publications.
- [3] Golden, S. A. R. (2017). Attitude of Students and Teachers towards E-Learning-An Analysis. Recent Research in Social Science & Humanities, 1, 5-10.
- [4] AyodhyaP. (2007). Emotional problems in secondary school children and its relation to life events and scholastic achievement". Osmania University, Hyderabad.
- [5] Bansibihari & Surwade. (2006), "The effect on emotional maturity on teacher effectiveness", Edutract, 6(1).
- [6] Bhardwaj, J.s. (2012), perceived parental behavior in relation to emotional maturity among adolescents, journal of community Guidance & Research, 29 (1): 158-187.
- [7] Best, W.J & Khan, W.J. (2008). Research in Education. New Delhi: prentice Hall of India Publications.
- [8] Best, J.W., (1995), Research in education, New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India private limited.
- [9] Bandura, A. (1977). Social learning Theory. NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [10] Golden, S. A. R., & Regi, S. B. Mobile Learning: A Transformative Tool for Learning and Education.
- [11] Chidiebre Kelechi Duru et al (2015). Attitude to aggressive Behavior and Intention of Aggressive Behaviour among Adolescent School Children in Selanger state Maqlaysia. Research on Humanities and School Children in Selangor state Malaysia. Research on Humanities and Social Sciences, Vol.5
- [12] Crow & crow, (2008). Child Development and adjustment, surjeet publication Delhi.